

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17394724

Influence of User Experience on Facility Use Behaviour at Ken Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic, Bori

Deekor, Nwite & Ekenta, Chukwuemeka E

**Department of Estate Management,
Faculty of Environmental Sciences,
Rivers State University, Nkporlu-Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.**

ABSTRACT

This study examines how user experience influences responsible facility use within public institutions, focusing on Ken Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic, Bori. The objectives were to assess the level of user experience among different categories of facility users and determine how this experience affects responsible behavior toward facility use. A qualitative case study design was adopted, using semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, and participant observation to gather data from staff, students, facility managers, and maintenance officers. Data were analyzed thematically to identify patterns and insights. Findings reveal that user experience, defined by exposure, orientation, and familiarity with institutional systems, significantly shapes responsible facility use. However, weak maintenance culture, limited supervision, and inadequate sensitization efforts hinder positive behavioral outcomes. The study concludes that institutional culture and management responsiveness mediate the relationship between user experience and responsible facility use. It recommends structured user orientation, regular sensitization programs, improved maintenance culture, participatory management, and strict enforcement of facility-use policies to promote sustainable facility management.

Keywords: User Experience, Facility Management, Responsible Behavior, Public Institutions, Ken Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic

1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria, for the right to life of everyone living in the country to be guaranteed, and that compels basic needs of people which are connected to public facilities to be provided. Accordingly, it is always the responsibility of government to provide public facilities because if left in the hands of private investors, they would not be able to sustain them without taking into account the profit accruable, and that could make it difficult to be affordable to everyone.

Public facilities within tertiary institutions play a vital role in enhancing academic productivity, administrative efficiency, and overall institutional sustainability. These facilities—ranging from lecture halls, libraries, laboratories, hostels, and recreational spaces—require proper use and maintenance by all categories of end users to ensure longevity and continued functionality. However, across many public institutions in Nigeria, misuse, neglect, and poor maintenance of facilities remain prevalent challenges that compromise service delivery and institutional effectiveness (Adewunmi, Omirin, & Famuyiwa, 2018). This persistent issue suggests that user behavior significantly influences facility condition and performance, and such behavior may, in turn, be shaped by users' experiences and perceptions.

User experience encompasses individuals' accumulated knowledge, exposure, and interaction with facilities, which influence how they perceive their roles and responsibilities toward facility utilization (Ajayi & Omotayo, 2020). In public institutions like the Ken Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic, Bori, user experience could manifest in how students, academic staff, and administrative personnel interact with shared facilities—determining whether they adopt responsible or careless attitudes. Prior research has

shown that when users have prior exposure to well-managed facilities, they are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward maintenance and accountability (Oladokun, 2019). Conversely, inadequate user orientation and low experience levels often lead to misuse, vandalism, and the deterioration of public assets (Onifade & Ayedun, 2021).

Responsible facility use is a behavioral construct linked to the user's sense of ownership, awareness, and appreciation of the value of shared assets (Nkwoh, & Obodoechi, 2022). In institutional contexts, it refers to practices such as proper handling of equipment, compliance with facility use guidelines, and participation in reporting maintenance issues. Understanding the extent to which user experience predicts responsible facility use is critical to formulating policies and interventions that promote sustainability within public institutions.

At Ken Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic, Bori, as in many similar Nigerian polytechnics, there have been recurrent reports of rapid facility wear, inadequate maintenance culture, and user negligence (Etuk & Udoh, 2020). While funding constraints and institutional management issues are often highlighted, the role of user experience in influencing responsible facility behavior has received limited empirical attention. This study, therefore, seeks to bridge that gap by examining how user experience shapes the level of responsibility displayed by end users toward the use and maintenance of public facilities within the Polytechnic. Insights from this study will aid institutional managers, facility managers, and policymakers in developing user-focused strategies to improve facility management efficiency and sustainability.

2. Aim of the Study

The study aims to examine how user experience determines responsible facility use within public institutions, using Ken Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic, Bori as a case study.

3 LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Concept of User Experience

User experience in the context of facility management refers to the totality of an individual's interaction with a facility, encompassing their prior knowledge, skills, perception, and satisfaction derived from its use (Ajayi & Omotayo, 2020). It goes beyond mere physical interaction to include the cognitive and emotional responses users develop toward the built environment. In public institutions, user experience is shaped by exposure to facility management practices, the quality of infrastructural amenities, and user orientation or training on facility use (Nkwoh & Obodoechi, 2022).

According to Norman (2013), user experience is influenced by three dimensions: usability, functionality, and emotional response. Usability concerns how efficiently users can operate facilities; functionality relates to whether facilities meet user needs; and emotional response involves how users feel about their interactions. In public facilities such as lecture halls, hostels, or laboratories, positive experiences enhance user satisfaction and promote responsible behavior, while negative experiences often lead to neglect, vandalism, or misuse.

In Nigerian tertiary institutions, user experience is frequently undermined by poor maintenance culture, inadequate facility design, and insufficient user education (Oladokun, 2019). Therefore, improving user experience through training, engagement, and participatory management is vital to promoting accountability and sustainable facility use.

3.2 Concept of Responsible Facility Use

Responsible facility use denotes the conscious and ethical utilization of shared institutional resources in a manner that ensures functionality, longevity, and equity of access (Adewunmi, Omirin, & Famuyiwa, 2018). It reflects the user's sense of stewardship and awareness of their role in maintaining the quality of public assets. Nkwoh and Obodoechi (2022) define responsible use as behavior that aligns with institutional policies on maintenance, safety, and resource conservation.

The key indicators of responsible facility use include adherence to facility rules, prompt reporting of faults, avoidance of misuse, and participation in maintenance initiatives. In academic environments, responsible use also involves observing cleanliness, conserving energy, and supporting peer awareness on proper facility handling (Etuk & Udoh, 2020).

Facility management literature emphasizes that responsible facility behavior among users reduces operational costs, improves longevity of infrastructure, and enhances environmental sustainability (Onifade & Ayedun, 2021). Thus, understanding the behavioral antecedents of responsible use such as experience, knowledge, and perception is essential for effective facility governance in public institutions.

3.3 Public Facilities: Overview

The concept of public facilities describes service or infrastructure provided for public and controlled by public authorities such as schools, libraries, hospitals, and emergency services, which are accessible to local inhabitants and have characteristics of public goods (IESBS, 2015). Facility is anything designed, built, installed, to serve a specific transition affording a convenience or service. The Collins Dictionary viewed it as buildings pieces of equipment or services that are provided for a particular purpose. Therefore, public facilities are the facilities or services provided by the government to the general public or citizens at large to use. The International Encyclopedia of Social and Behavioral Sciences, as presented in Gorter & Nijkamp (2015) defines Public facilities as being referred to as “services or infrastructures controlled by public authorities such as schools, library, hospitals, and emergency services with characteristics of public goods and are accessible to local inhabitants. Government’s main objective is to provide these public facilities to the citizens and businesses to manage social, economic and environmental activities more smoothly (Vendantu, 2022; UNEP, 2012).

Public facilities relate to people’s basic needs. Any modern society requires that these facilities are provided so that people’s basic needs are met. The right to life that the constitution guarantees is for all persons living in the country. The responsibility to provide public facilities therefore must be that of government which generates its revenue mainly from taxes collected from the people.

The important characteristics of public facilities are that, once it is provided, its benefits can be shared by many people. For instance, a school in the village will enable many children to get educated. Given that public facilities are so important, someone must carry the responsibility of providing these to the people. This someone is the government. One of the most important functions of the government is to ensure that these public facilities are made available to everyone which the private companies who operate for profit in the market rarely do. In most of the public facilities, there is no profit to be had. For example, what profit can accrue to a company for keeping the roads clean or running an anti-malaria campaign (Study ‘n’ Learn, 2021). A private company will probably not be interested in undertaking such work. But for the other public facilities such as schools and hospitals, private companies may well be interested.

3.4 Empirical Literature Review

Several empirical studies have explored the relationship between user experience, behavior, and facility management within public institutions, particularly in the Nigerian context. Collectively, these studies emphasize that responsible facility use depends not only on technical management systems but also on user experience, behavioral orientation, and institutional support.

Adewunmi, Omirin, and Famuyiwa (2018) examined facility management challenges in Nigerian tertiary institutions and found that inadequate maintenance funding, poor supervision, and minimal user involvement significantly affected facility performance. Their findings revealed that user negligence often stemmed from limited awareness and lack of training. They recommended the adoption of participatory maintenance strategies to enhance accountability and sustainability. Similarly, Ajayi and Omotayo (2020) investigated user perception and satisfaction in public building management and discovered that quick maintenance response and open communication between managers and users improved user satisfaction and responsible behavior. The study concluded that user experience and engagement directly influence the perceived quality and longevity of public facilities.

Etuk and Udoh (2020) explored infrastructure management in Nigerian polytechnics and identified poor user orientation and weak institutional accountability as core issues undermining effective facility management. They argued that user training and participatory practices can improve facility sustainability. In a related study, Nkwoh and Obodoechi (2022) established a strong relationship between user behavior and facility performance in public institutions, noting that users with prior experience or exposure to well-maintained systems exhibit more responsible behaviors. Their findings underscore the importance of experience-based learning and behavioral sensitization in promoting facility care.

Oladokun (2019) further linked the decline of maintenance culture in Nigerian universities to institutional neglect and inconsistent funding. The study revealed that when users operate within poorly maintained environments, their sense of responsibility diminishes. Conversely, proactive maintenance and awareness campaigns encourage responsible use and foster a culture of shared ownership. Supporting this view, Onifade and Ayedun (2021) found that user engagement in public building management enhances facility performance and compliance. Their study demonstrated that involving users in decision-making and maintenance processes nurtures a sense of ownership, thereby reducing vandalism and misuse.

Amaratunga and Baldry (2002) examined the shift from performance measurement to performance management in facility administration, showing that structured feedback and user engagement improve satisfaction, accountability, and sustainable facility use. They emphasized that participatory management and performance-based systems foster responsible behavior among users.

Douglas and Mills (2018) found that maintenance responsiveness strongly shapes user behavior neglected facilities lead to frustration and misuse, while prompt repairs and clear communication encourage responsibility and ownership. They concluded that well-maintained environments reinforce positive user conduct and extend facility lifespan.

Olanrewaju and Abdul-Aziz (2015) highlighted that weak maintenance culture, limited user involvement, and poor institutional policies accelerate facility deterioration in developing countries. Their findings showed that user participation and a sense of ownership significantly enhance sustainability, reducing misuse and promoting responsible facility management.

From a behavioral perspective, Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behavior explains that responsible facility use is influenced by user attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and institutional norms. Similarly, Kolb's (2014) Experiential Learning Theory and Bandura's (1977) Social Learning Theory affirm that users develop responsibility through experience, observation, and feedback within their environment. These theoretical positions are empirically supported by Nkwoh and Obodoechi (2022) and Ajayi and Omotayo (2020), who both found that experiential exposure and institutional reinforcement improve facility-use behavior.

Norman (2013) emphasized the role of *user-centered design* in shaping positive user interaction with systems and facilities. Applying this concept to institutional environments, the usability and accessibility of facilities influence user satisfaction and responsible engagement. Likewise, Proshansky (1978) proposed the notion of *place identity*, suggesting that users' emotional connection to their institutional environment affects how they relate to and care for its physical structures. This is evident in Onifade and Ayedun's (2021) findings, which showed that emotionally and socially engaged users demonstrate greater facility stewardship.

Collectively, these empirical studies confirm that user experience, exposure, and institutional culture are critical determinants of responsible facility behavior. They also highlight that experience alone is insufficient unless complemented by proactive maintenance culture, user sensitization, and participatory management. Strengthening these mediating factors can therefore promote sustainable facility management and enhance public infrastructure performance in institutions such as Ken Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic, Bori.

4 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a qualitative case study design to examine how user experience influences responsible facility use at Ken Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic, Bori. The qualitative approach was chosen for its capacity to capture participants' subjective experiences and contextual behaviors (Leavy, 2014; Creswell, 2014). The case study method provided a framework for exploring the phenomenon within its real-life institutional environment (Flyvbjerg, 2006).

Data were obtained from primary and secondary sources. Primary data collection involved semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, and participant observation, while secondary data were drawn from institutional reports and relevant literature. Three focus group sessions were conducted, engaging facility managers and maintenance personnel of Estate and Works, student representatives, and staff. Semi-structured interviews with 21 respondents comprising 8 staff and 8 students provided deeper

insights into management practices and user behaviors, and participant observation allowed firsthand assessment of facility use (Osuala, 2005).

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants with direct experience and knowledge of facility management and use (Black, 2010). To ensure validity and reliability, instruments and procedures were reviewed by experts, while data triangulation enhanced credibility (Noble & Heale, 2019; Middleton, 2019).

Data were analyzed using thematic and narrative analysis, involving systematic coding and interpretation to identify recurring patterns and themes. The analysis emphasized understanding how user experience, shaped by institutional exposure and facility familiarity, affects responsible behavior in public facility use.

5. PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The focus group discussion comprised 4 academic staff selected purposively from the School of Applied Sciences, Environmental Technology, Management Sciences and Engineering. One (1) facility manager, 3 maintenance officers from the Department of works, and 2 students each from the four schools of Ken Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic, Bori. The facility managers and maintenance officers served as key participants, providing vital insights into facility management practices and user-related challenges, while academic and non-academic staff, along with students, contributed perspectives from their daily interactions with campus facilities. This diverse group reflected varying levels of facility usage and responsibility, offering a comprehensive understanding of how user experience and institutional practices influence responsible behavior in the use and management of public facilities within the Polytechnic.

5.1 Focus Group Discussion and Interview Responses on User Experience among Facility Users

5.1.1. Academic Staff

During the focus group sessions, many staff participants described their experience with public facilities as *“largely average but improving.”* They noted that although most facilities such as lecture halls, offices, and laboratories were functional, maintenance lapses and limited user orientation affected their usability. One senior lecturer stated:

“Most of us have learned to manage with what we have, but the facilities are not always user-friendly, especially when repairs are delayed. We rely more on experience than proper guidance”.

Administrative staff expressed similar concerns, emphasizing that previous exposure to modern facilities elsewhere influenced their expectations and behavior. A registry officer remarked:

“Those who have worked in better-equipped institutions tend to handle facilities more carefully because they know the cost of neglect”.

Overall, staff demonstrated moderate to high levels of user experience, often shaped by professional exposure and institutional responsibility.

5.1.2 Students

Students' discussions revealed diverse levels of user experience depending on department, level of study, and prior exposure to facility use. New students admitted limited understanding of proper facility handling, often attributing misuse to lack of induction. A participant from the Science Laboratory Technology Department said:

“We were not taught how to use some of the equipment; we just follow what others do”.

Final-year students, however, showed greater awareness and responsibility. One noted:

“After three years here, you learn how to use the lecture hall furniture and lab instruments properly, mainly through observation and experience”.

Nevertheless, several students agreed that lack of supervision and inadequate maintenance culture contributed to the deterioration of facilities, reducing motivation for responsible use.

5.1.3 Facility Managers and Maintenance Personnel

Facility managers and estate staff provided a managerial perspective, observing that user experience correlates with frequency of facility use and access to orientation. According to one maintenance officer:

“Users who attend workshops or interact closely with us tend to use facilities better. The problem is that many don't attend such sensitizations.”

Another respondent added:

“Some users treat public property as nobody’s business. Experience comes only when there is a sense of ownership”.

They concluded that user experience among facility users is uneven, with administrative staff generally demonstrating the highest competence, while students, especially new entrants, exhibit the lowest.

Table 5.1: Summary of Focus Group Discussion and Interview Responses on User Experience

Theme	Category of Respondents	Key Observations	Quotes
General Use Familiarity	Facility and Academic & Staff	Most staff described their facility use experience as moderate to high. Familiarity came from routine engagement and institutional exposure.	“Most of us have learned to manage with what we have, but the facilities are not always user-friendly, especially when repairs are delayed.” – <i>Senior Lecturer</i>
Influence of Prior Exposure	Academic Staff	Those with prior experience in better-equipped environments showed greater care and understanding of facility handling.	“Those who have worked in better-equipped institutions tend to handle facilities more carefully because they know the cost of neglect.” – <i>Registry Officer</i>
Limited Orientation Among New Users	Students (ND I & ND II)	Many new students lacked formal guidance on facility use and relied on observation.	“We were not taught how to use some of the equipment; we just follow what others do.” – <i>Science Lab Tech Student</i>
Experience through Longevity Practice	Senior Students and (HND II)	Older students displayed improved responsibility from accumulated experience over time.	“After three years here, you learn how to use the lecture hall furniture and lab instruments properly, mainly through observation and experience.” – <i>HND II Student</i>
Impact of Maintenance Culture	Students & Staff	Poor maintenance and delayed repairs discouraged proper use and reduced ownership sense.	“Sometimes facilities are already broken before we use them; that makes people careless.” – <i>Student Participant</i>
Training Sensitization Effect	and Facility Managers & Estate Staff	Orientation and training programs were found to significantly influence user experience and responsible use.	“Users who attend workshops or interact closely with us tend to use facilities better.” – <i>Estate Officer</i>
Sense of Ownership Attitude	and Facility Managers	A weak sense of ownership among users was linked to irresponsible behavior and misuse.	“Some users treat public property as nobody’s business. Experience comes only when there is a sense of ownership.” – <i>Maintenance Officer</i>

Source: Field Survey, 2025

5.2 Focus Group Discussion and Interview Responses on Influence of User Experience on Facility Use Behavior

5.2.1 Academic Staff

Most academic and administrative staff strongly agreed that user experience significantly influences responsible behavior in facility use. Staff with longer service years and prior exposure to facility management exhibited greater awareness of proper usage, maintenance, and reporting culture.

A senior lecturer explained:

“Experience makes a big difference. Those who understand the cost of maintaining these facilities use them more carefully and encourage others to do the same”

Another lecturer added:

“When people know how facilities work and what happens when they misuse them, they act more responsibly. It’s often ignorance or lack of experience that causes damage”.

However, a few participants noted that even experienced users sometimes exhibit negligence due to institutional fatigue or weak enforcement mechanisms, implying that experience alone may not fully ensure responsible behavior.

5.2.2 Students

Students’ responses showed that user experience plays a gradual but notable role in shaping responsible facility use. New students often lacked knowledge of proper conduct in classrooms, hostels, and laboratories. In contrast, final-year students with longer exposure demonstrated better care and understanding of institutional facilities.

One ND I student admitted:

“When I first came, I didn’t know there were rules about handling chairs or lab equipment. We just followed others”.

Meanwhile, a final-year student noted:

“Over time, you learn that when you destroy something, everyone suffers because it’s not replaced quickly. That experience makes you more carefu..”

Despite this, several students emphasized that lack of supervision, inadequate maintenance, and peer influence sometimes undermine responsible behavior even among experienced users.

5.2.3 Facility Managers and Maintenance Staff

Facility management staff unanimously highlighted those users with higher facility exposure and practical experience demonstrate more responsibility in reporting faults, preventing misuse, and participating in upkeep activities.

A facility officer stated:

“We notice that staff and students who have attended our sensitization workshops behave more responsibly; they switch off lights, lock rooms, and report faults quickly”.

However, another maintenance officer observed that institutional culture and leadership influence are also critical:

“Experience helps, but without management enforcing responsibility, even the experienced ones sometimes relax and join others in careless habits”.

They concluded that while user experience fosters responsible use, institutional policies and attitudes toward accountability amplify or diminish its effects.

Table 5.2: Summary of Focus Group Discussion and Interview Responses on the Influence of User Experience on Responsible Facility Use

Theme	Category of Respondents	Key Observations	Illustrative Quotes
Influence of Experience on Facility Care	Academic & Non-Academic Staff	Experienced users show greater care and awareness in handling institutional facilities due to familiarity with their operational and maintenance processes.	<i>“Experience makes a big difference. Those who understand the cost of maintaining these facilities use them more carefully and encourage others to do the same.” – Senior Lecturer</i>
Knowledge and Awareness through Exposure	Administrative Staff	Prior training or exposure to similar institutions promotes more responsible and preventive facility-use behavior.	<i>“When people know how facilities work and what happens when they misuse them, they act more responsibly.” – Admin Officer</i>

Theme	Category of Respondents	Key Observations	Illustrative Quotes
Low Responsibility among New Users	Students (ND I & ND II)	New students with limited user experience tend to misuse facilities due to ignorance or peer influence.	“When I first came, I didn’t know there were rules about handling chairs or lab equipment. We just followed others.” – <i>ND I Student</i>
Progressive Learning through Experience	Senior Students (HND II)	Longer exposure to facility use increases responsible behavior, especially when linked to consequences of misuse.	“Over time, you learn that when you destroy something, everyone suffers because it’s not replaced quickly. That experience makes you more careful.” – <i>HND II Student</i>
Institutional Support and Enforcement	Facility Managers & Maintenance Staff	While experience promotes responsibility, weak monitoring systems and enforcement reduce users’ sense of accountability.	“Experience helps, but without enforcing responsibility, even the experienced ones sometimes relax and join others in careless habits.” – <i>Maintenance Officer</i>
Training and Sensitization Effects	Facility Managers	Training and user sensitization greatly improve responsible use among both staff and students.	“We notice that staff and students who have attended our sensitization workshops behave more responsibly—they switch off lights, lock rooms, and report faults quickly.” – <i>Facility Officer</i>
Moderating Role of Institutional Culture	All Categories	Institutional attitudes toward maintenance and discipline shape how effectively experience translates into responsible behavior.	“Experience alone is not enough; people act responsibly when they see that management also values and maintains facilities.” – <i>Facility Manager</i>

Source: Field Survey, 2025

6. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings reveal that user experience significantly shapes responsible behavior toward public facility use, with variations across staff and student categories. Academic and non-academic staff reported moderate to high familiarity with institutional facilities due to routine engagement, but poor maintenance practices often dampened motivation for careful use. This supports Amaratunga and Baldry (2002), who noted that inadequate maintenance environments reduce user satisfaction and behavioral responsibility.

Administrative staff linked responsible behavior to prior exposure to better-managed systems, aligning with Kolb’s Experiential Learning Theory (1984), which posits that individuals apply lessons from previous experiences. Conversely, new students (ND I & ND II) demonstrated lower responsibility levels due to limited orientation and reliance on peer modeling, reflecting Ajzen’s Theory of Planned Behavior (1991), which ties behavioral control to awareness and environment. Senior students (HND II), however, displayed improved facility management behavior through progressive social learning, consistent with Bandura’s (1977) framework.

Both staff and students cited weak institutional maintenance culture as a major deterrent to responsible behavior, resonating with Douglas and Mills (2018), who emphasized that maintenance responsiveness enhances user ownership. Facility managers observed that users who attended sensitization programs demonstrated greater care, underscoring the value of continuous education. Furthermore, a shared sense of ownership was identified as a key factor influencing responsibility, supporting Olanrewaju and Abdul-Aziz (2015) that participatory facility management fosters accountability.

In summary, user experience at Ken Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic directly influences responsible facility behavior, but this relationship is moderated by institutional culture, training, and maintenance practices.

Strengthening these mediating factors through sustained orientation, enforcement, and participatory engagement could promote a culture of responsibility and sustainability in facility management.

7. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that user experience plays a critical role in shaping responsible behavior toward the use of public facilities at Ken Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic, Bori. Staff and students' levels of exposure, orientation, and familiarity with institutional systems significantly influence how responsibly they interact with facilities. However, the presence of a weak maintenance culture, inadequate supervision, and limited sensitization programs undermines these positive behaviors. The findings affirm that institutional culture and management responsiveness are vital mediating factors that transform user experience into sustained responsible practices.

To promote responsible facility, use and sustainable management, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Strengthen User Orientation: The institution should implement structured orientation programs for new students and staff to instill awareness of proper facility use and maintenance ethics.
- ii. Promote Continuous Sensitization: Regular workshops and campaigns should be organized to reinforce responsible behavior and deepen user understanding of facility value.
- iii. Enhance Maintenance Culture: Prompt maintenance and visible management responsiveness will motivate users to take ownership and maintain facilities appropriately.
- iv. Encourage Participatory Management: Users should be actively involved in facility management decisions to enhance their sense of ownership and accountability.
- v. Enforce Institutional Policies: Clear rules, supervision, and sanctions for misuse should be established to deter negligence and reinforce responsible behavior.

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